

NANOCOMPOSITES AND NANO-ENGINEERED COMPOSITES REINFORCED WITH ALIGNED CARBON NANOTUBES (INVITED)

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SUMMARY

Advanced composites can be engineered at the nanoscale to achieve significant macroscopic engineering property enhancement and tailoring. Aligned carbon nanotube (CNT) integration into polymer matrices of existing fibrous laminated aerospace material systems, with emphasis on scaling and fabrication routes, is reviewed in the context of measured bulk multifunctional properties such as laminate strength, toughness, and electrical and thermal conductivities. Such results motivate study of aligned-CNT polymer nanocomposites (PNCs), which form the hybridized portion of the 3D-reinforced nano-engineered bulk composites. In addition to forming the hybrid matrix component in the macroscopic composites, aligned-CNT PNCs (A-PNCs) are interesting new composites themselves, with applications in many areas such as thermal interfaces, and perhaps as structural elements at high CNT volume fractions. This paper focuses on recent work fabricating, testing, and modeling continuous A-PNCs. Fabrication of controlled-morphology PNCs using a novel procedure allows such PNCs to be studied at volume fractions exceeding 20%. As an example, axial modulus (along the CNT axis) is shown to be in good agreement with basic “rule-of-mixtures” mechanics when CNT ‘waviness’ is considered. Thermal transport studies highlight the dominant role of nano-scale thermal boundary resistance (TBR) in effective non-isotropic conductivities of the PNCs. In addition to numerous nano-engineered composite topics, ongoing work seeks to link individual CNT and matrix properties to measured PNC properties.

Keywords: carbon nanotube, CNT, hybrid, processing, fabrication, scaling, representative volume element, polymer matrix composites, thermal conductivity

INTRODUCTION

Nano-engineered composites are created using aligned CNTs in the polymer matrix to hybridize existing advanced composites. These hybrid systems have several

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architectures (see example in Fig. 1) as well as processing routes (hand lay-up, prepreg, infusion) that have recently been demonstrated. While property enhancement has been demonstrated and possible mechanisms identified, key gaps still exist in linking nano- and micro-structural physical properties to bulk measured properties. These gaps must be closed if improved designs of such nano-engineered composites are to be realized. In addition to models addressing multi-scale design, fundamental physical properties needed as inputs to the overall design problem are still missing, *e.g.*, modulus and strength of aligned-CNT reinforced aerospace-grade polymers, and CNT-CNT thermal boundary resistances. Various efforts in our group to establish such properties for A-PNCs [1-5], are discussed focusing on scale-dependent and intrinsic properties of PNCs and how those can be used to engineer bulk properties. Enhanced bulk engineering properties measured recently [6-8] are reviewed as motivation for understanding the underlying physical properties and interface contributions of the A-PNCs.

NANO-ENGINEERED COMPOSITES

Aligned CNTs are a second fiber by which to create a hybrid fiber-reinforced composite with multi-scale (sometimes called hierarchical) ‘fiber’ reinforcement: CNTs at the nanoscale and traditional advanced fibers at the microscale. Aligned CNTs provide a capillary-driven mechanism to consolidate the composite, a process that has been shown to be effective with a variety of unmodified polymer systems, including hand lay-up epoxy resins and aerospace-grade infusion resins (*e.g.*, RTM6 form Hexcel) [9,10]. The aligned CNTs and capillary-driven polymer wetting mechanism avoid many of the issues associated with dispersing/mixing CNTs in polymers, which is typically done before introducing the modified resin into the fiber form or at the ply interface. Work in the area of mixing nanomaterials in resins to create PNCs and hybrid composites is extensive and is not reviewed here [11-19]. Intrinsic and scale-dependent characteristics of CNTs have been used to engineer significant laminate-level property improvements: interlaminar shear strength, interlaminar toughness, electrical and thermal conductivity experimental results for the architecture shown in Fig. 1 have been reported (a summary is included in [20]).

A closed-form analytic model [21] has been developed for the interlaminar Mode I fracture toughness of composite plies reinforced with aligned CNTs, such as those in the ‘nanostitch’ architecture [7]. The fracture model is in agreement with prior numerical work [22] on the same configuration, and clearly shows the scale effect on the magnitude of interlaminar toughness improvement, wherein nanoscale reinforcing fibers are advantaged over larger scale fibers/tows used in traditional stitching, braiding, and z-pinning. The enhancement in toughness is given by the ratio of the steady-state toughness (G_{ss}) of the interface with bridging CNTs, to the toughness of the interface without reinforcement (G_0) [21]:

$$\frac{G_{ss}}{G_0} = 1 + \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{L_f}{r_f} \right) \left(\frac{V_f \tau L_f}{G_0} \right) \quad (1)$$

where L_f , r_f , and V_f are the length, radius, and volume fraction of the fiber, respectively, and τ is the interfacial (sliding) shear stress between the reinforcing fiber and the polymer matrix. The scale dependence of the fiber on toughening, given by the inverse of the aspect ratio, favors small radii fibers such as CNTs. Limiting the toughening is

the strength of the reinforcing fiber, which suggests that nanoscale fibers of high strength (such as CNTs) are ideal bridging elements for toughness enhancement. Recent work has applied this model to the FFRP architecture [23]. Load-transfer at the critical fiber-matrix interface, where the matrix is modified by the aligned CNTs creating a radially transversely isotropic matrix, has also been analyzed and the effect of reduced interfacial maximum shear stress quantified [24]. In addition to mechanics of these nano-engineered composites, continuous (rather than batch) manufacturing [25] has been developed and environmental exposure studies [26-28] undertaken. The nano-engineered composite results and prior work provide the context for exploring the properties of A-PNCs because such PNCs are a part of a representative volume element (RVE) [29] in the nano-engineered composite matrix (see Fig. 2).

Fig. 1. An example of a 3-dimensional CNT-reinforced composite: a ‘fuzzy-fiber’ composite with *in situ*-grown radially-aligned CNTs on the woven cloth. In addition to this fuzzy-fiber reinforced plastic (FFRP) architecture, a ‘nanostitched’ architecture for prepreg systems has also been reported [7].

Fig. 2. Aligned-CNT polymer nanocomposite (A-PNC) as a hybrid matrix representative volume element (RVE) of a nano-engineered (hybrid) composite.

POLYMER NANOCOMPOSITES WITH CONTROLLED MORPHOLOGY

Outstanding questions related to CNT contributions to PNC properties are numerous, and typically new research results must be interpreted very carefully due to the strong effects of processing parameters on the resulting PNC. Damage to CNT-based PNCs when the CNTs are mixed (often in ‘high-shear’ processes) is difficult to characterize. Random orientation and agglomeration/aggregation and inhomogeneous distributions abound, and chemical or other surface coatings strongly influence many physical properties due to the high surface-to-volume ratios in nano-scale constituents such as CNTs. Consider the difference in fiber spacing between micron-scale fibers and nano-scale fibers (CNTs) as shown in Fig. 3 [10]: fiber spacing approaches 10’s of nm to achieve high volume fractions (>50%) when packing nanoscale fibers (see shaded region in Fig. 3), whereas traditional (such as 7 μm carbon) fibers achieve high volume fraction with much greater inter-fiber distances.

The nanostructure/fiber spacing is important particularly for PNCs, as in the nm-range, we approach characteristic lengths of the polymer chains. Therefore, PNCs at high volume fraction require extremely straight and tightly (nm-scale control) spaced reinforcing fibers (we focus here on CNTs) where the space between the reinforcements is smaller than, or of the same order, as polymer chain lengths. Clearly, as state-of-the-art in processing PNCs relies on mixing, nm-control of collimation and packing is a significant challenge simply to achieve a high packing of CNTs similar to carbon fibers. Furthermore, nanostructured fillers, esp. CNTs, act to alter polymer morphology (packing, crystallinity etc.) local to the nanostructure. The extent and degree of alteration of the polymer are still subjects of research and will depend on specifics of the nanostructured reinforcement (*e.g.*, presence of molecules adhered to the nanostructure surface), the polymers, and processing parameters of the PNC, but two things are clear: (a) nanostructures can initiate significant crystallinity in some thermoplastics, *e.g.*, [30, 31], and more broadly a region of altered polymer morphology (and properties) exists local to the nanostructure with characteristic lengths estimated to be on the order of 10-100 nm [32,33] for both thermosets and thermoplastics; and (b) even if CNTs are aligned, they are not collimated as in typical aerospace systems like carbon fiber prepreg, but rather the CNTs have significant ‘waviness’ [34]. If the estimations of altered polymer extent are correct, PNCs of even low volume fraction have significant, if not 100%, matrix that is altered (*e.g.*, if $x = 20$ nm is the region of altered polymer, then all PNCs with diameters less than 10 nm in Fig. 3 will have ~100% altered matrix). Our group has investigated the altered polymer matrix topic using wide-angle x-ray scattering (WAXS) and observed no discernible polymer morphology changes for one thermoset [10], but significant crystallinity in one thermoplastic (PVA) due to the presence of 8 nm diameter multi-wall CNTs (MWNTs) at varying volume fractions up to 20% aligned CNTs.

Here we consider further a well-controlled and characterized aligned-PNC system consisting of as-grown (unfunctionalized) *continuous* MWNTs (average 8 nm in dia.) in an aerospace-grade thermoset epoxy (RTM6, Hexcel) matrix. A novel process for controlling volume fraction while maintaining CNT alignment is used to investigate

nanoscale interactions and effective properties for aligned-CNT volume fractions of 1, 8, and 20% (see points on Fig. 3) [12]. As stated previously, no polymer morphology changes have been observed for this PNC system in WAXS analyses. The most recent findings from ongoing investigations into mechanical, electrical and thermal properties of this mm-scale continuous A-PNC are briefly introduced, focusing on key non-isotropic physical properties such as modulus and effective thermal conductivity along and perpendicular to the CNT axis. As in traditional composites, alignment of the reinforcing fibers is critical to optimizing and tailoring properties, *e.g.*, modulus [35]. Modulus is measured via standard nanoindentation techniques and an apparent, or indentation modulus [36], is extracted using the standard Oliver-Pharr theory ignoring the non-isotropic nature of the material.

Fig. 3. Scale-dependence of volume fraction on inter-fiber spacing of aligned-reinforcement composites highlighting differences between CNTs and micron-scale fibers (typical $\sim 7 \mu\text{m}$ diameter fibers like carbon). Simple square packing assumed.

The A-PNCs show a linearly increasing trend in effective modulus with volume fraction, V_f , (see Fig. 4) including the highest reported value (at 20% V_f) for epoxy PNCs [37]. Even though the effective modulus is large, it is still far ($\sim 10X$ less) from the expected modulus (~ 100 GPa, assuming a CNT modulus of 500 GPa) estimated from simple rule of mixtures. A dominant morphological effect, CNT waviness, is taken into account by other authors in modeling of such an A-PNCs [38-40] where waviness is predicted to have a significant effect on PNC modulus. Fisher *et al.* [39] modified simple rule of mixtures models by finite element analysis and calculated a wavy CNT modulus where the CNTs have a sinusoidal form as a function of amplitude and wavelength ratio (a/λ). SEM images of 1% V_f CNTs (see example in Fig. 5) were used to evaluate the waviness ratio of our aligned-CNT forests used to fabricate the A-PNCs [34]. The waviness ratio is calculated from several SEM images to be $a/\lambda = 0.131 \pm 0.1$ and is appropriately transformed into 3D to yield an average $a/\lambda = 0.185 \pm 0.1$. The

effective modulus predicted for this waviness ratio in [39] was used to predict the A-PNCs modulus values through rule of mixtures for 1, 8 and 20% V_f A-PNCs and compared with the experimental results from nanoindentation. The predicted results for indentation modulus (e.g., 9-10 GPa at 20% V_f) are in good agreement with the experimental values (e.g., 8.8 GPa at 20% V_f). CNT waviness is seen as the dominant effect in reducing the modified rule-of-mixtures estimation of modulus giving predictions that are in excellent agreement with the experiments. Also considered here is the effect of the distribution in waviness ratio, where the effect of one standard deviation (SD) of the measured waviness is shown in Fig. 4.

Fig. 4. Predicted effective modulus including CNT waviness vs. volume fraction, including the effect of ± 1 SD variation from average waviness, after [34].

Fig. 5. Example SEM image used for estimation of aligned-CNT forest waviness ratio [34]. Markings indicate curves used to estimate waviness amplitude and wavelength.

In addition to mechanical properties of the A-PNCs, non-isotropic electrical [34] and thermal conductivity are also of interest. Important in understanding electrical and thermal transport of PNCs is the interface resistance to transport at the CNT-polymer and CNT-CNT interfaces (in addition to the altered properties of the matrix discussed above) [33, 41]. Interfaces are important for both electrical (*e.g.*, [42, 43]) and thermal conductivity due to surface-to-volume scaling of nano-scale fillers, but is particularly dominant in thermal conduction.

Fig. 6. Aligned (collimated) CNT PNC simulation results of heat conduction, including CNT-CNT and CNT-matrix thermal boundary resistance, after [44].

In recent work, we have focused modeling efforts on understanding the role of morphology and thermal boundary resistance, TBR (both CNT-matrix and CNT-CNT) on thermal conductivities [44-46]. Non-isotropic (directional) thermal conductivities of A-PNCs were calculated using a random walk simulation with and without inter-CNT contact effects [44]. The effects of CNT orientation, type (single vs. multi-wall), inter-CNT contact, volume fraction and TBR on the effective conductivities of CNT-composites have been simulated. CNT-CNT and CNT-matrix TBRs (see illustration in Fig. 6) are shown to significantly affect the effective transport properties including anisotropy ratios (see Fig. 6). Experimental TBR data is both limited and uncertain in the literature, such that TBRs have been perhaps best calculated from models, *e.g.*, molecular dynamics [47]. The CNT-matrix thermal barrier resistance (TBR) is shown to be a critical parameter in determining effective conductivities. CNT-CNT contact is shown to decrease effective thermal conductivity along the CNT axis (Fig. 6 left) whereas it can enhance conductivity in the transverse direction (Fig. 6 right). At a critical value of CNT-matrix TBR, addition of conducting materials to a polymer can

reduce effective thermal conductivity of the matrix rather than increase it (see Fig. 6 right). The role of CNT-matrix and CNT-CNT interactions need significant further experimental and theoretical investigations, particularly as these same issues are relevant not only to PNCs, but also for nano-engineered composites (see RVE in Fig. 2).

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Both nano-engineered composites (hybrids of traditional composites) and polymer nanocomposites (PNCs) using aligned carbon nanotubes (CNTs) have been described, particularly focusing on the role of morphology on effective physical properties of these multi-scale material systems. In macroscopic (traditional) laminated composites, interlaminar fracture toughness is best enhanced by reinforcement with nanoscale (CNT) ‘fibers’ due to the scale dependence of this enhancement. PNCs are useful and relevant engineering materials, and are also important to study as a component of the nano-engineered composite systems. Critical to understanding properties of PNCs are more comprehensive experimental-theoretical comparisons, which to date are scarce and open to multiple interpretations due to the difficulty in quantifying critical features in the PNC, such as dispersion (agglomeration), morphology, and the several effects associated with polymer interphases and interfaces. A particularly useful system to study is that of an aligned-CNT PNC (A-PNC), which forms the hybrid matrix the nano-engineered bulk composites. Experimental and theoretical results are reviewed and presented for fabricating and modeling A-PNCs, with new insight gained as demonstrated by the dominant effect of CNT waviness on the modulus of A-PNCs along the CNT axis. Future work in these areas has been highlighted throughout the manuscript.

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